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CRITERIA OF EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTI-CRISIS STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF INNOVATIVE COMPANIES OF GEORGIA AND EU COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The challenges of the 21st century force us to always be in shape, to perceive and control the rapidly changing environment and to react correctly to the processes taking place in it.

In today's world, in an open and global information space, where there is a constant and diverse exchange of thoughts and ideas, where there are no restrictions and critical content is quite common, all types of innovative companies are vulnerable to the spread of negative information, which, of course, affects their reputation and business it damages the image.

The purpose of the present study is to analyze the criteria of the effectiveness of the anti-crisis strategic management of the innovative company at the modern stage and to search for ways of further development. The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is the works, articles, as well as materials, publications, internet resources of the relevant problems of national and foreign scientists, where the analysis and evaluation of the practical experience of the innovative companies of Georgia and the EU countries is reflected.

The article proposes both the stages of the anti-crisis management process of the innovative company and the supporting measures for planning the anti-crisis campaign.

In this paper, the functions of risk management are highlighted, the positive and negative aspects of anti-crisis strategic management of an innovative company at the modern stage are determined; Also, as a conclusion, efficiency criteria are established to improve the above-mentioned processes in the long term.

Keywords: Anti-crisis, Strategic, Management, Innovative, Company.

As is known, the world community has accumulated considerable experience in creating legislation on bankruptcy (insolvency). More or less, innovative companies operating in the European Union countries have a rich experience of the bankruptcy procedure.

It is worth noting that communication crises of different scales are part of the normal agenda and each of them needs the correct anti-crisis communication designed for long-term results, since in modern conditions the probability of a crisis in the strategic management of innovative companies is relevant, which can arise both spontaneously and slowly. This process requires methods of overcoming it and peculiarities of study. In particular, the company's anti-crisis management should determine the set of developed measures and optimization. Here it is important for successful manage-

ment what to do and act at each stage of the crisis, because the cause of all crises is ineffective management. However, a crisis can be caused by the low qualification of the manager, the wrong allocation of financial resources or planning, causing irreversible consequences and bringing the company to the brink of bankruptcy.

Globalization in the society and thinking of the modern world creates special conditions for all spheres of human life and work. Accordingly, the strategic management of modern companies is growing. The biggest challenge today is leadership development, workforce diversity (technologies), which directly or indirectly affects the competitiveness of the organization. The effective and important method of the company is the selected group of employees. Among the management methods, it is worth noting:

- ❖ Responsibility - the activity of employees, to have an adequate reaction to the social response-protection, which is related to the sustainable and economic progress of the company;

- ❖ Focusing on long-term goals - adapting to innovative and technological changes based on the interests of the company;

- ❖ Ensuring introduction of talents in the company - modern requirements of knowledge and qualifications compatible with globalization in relation to personal qualities, since the expectations of employers and employees are constantly changing and this process must be consistent with the strategy;

- ❖ Creating motivation to improve the company - career development, more independence and activities, offering flexible work schedule, appropriate pay for overtime work;

- ❖ Ensuring the rationality of strategic management - which means compliance of incurred expenses with the obtained result. In particular, targeted preparation of human resources - retraining, introduction and management of employee-oriented culture.

The company's development perspective and operation is determined by its ability and ability to correctly determine expected changes in a crisis situation, since the possibility of bankruptcy will be avoided. The part of companies that do not take into account the critical situation and make mistakes often fail. It is the country's obligation to take complex and reasonable measures to ensure that companies in such a situation overcome the crisis, so that the company does not reach liquidation, since at the current stage, enterprises have to operate in unstable environmental conditions with risk factors. It is sad, but true, that the country does not have a state policy in this direction.

Anti-crisis management is a PR direction that develops a framework plan for predicting and eliminating possible crisis situations; formulates strategies to attend to the impending crisis and stop it; and in crisis conditions, it manages the communication process, which is focused on the development of the organization's position, and also affects the perception of the problem; Prevents the spread of misinformation, neutralizes and minimizes the consequences of the crisis. The pinnacle of professionalism is not only to focus on problem management to protect the organization from the influence of internal facts, but also for the innovative company to benefit from the strengthening of its business activity at the expense of neutralizing the facts that threaten the advantages that it has. An important element of anti-crisis management in the company's system is determined by its result. In particular, how to act at all stages of the crisis. The anti-crisis management process includes:

- Pre-crisis management;
- Crisis management;
- Post-crisis actions;
- Decisions.

Naturally, it is very interesting how the anti-crisis campaign there is planned. When identifying a crisis, it would be appropriate to take the following supportive measures:

- ✓ Creation of a working group and delegation of functions;

- ✓ Time planning of main actions;

- ✓ Identification of the causes of the situation;

- ✓ Creation of message boxes;

- ✓ Generating basic messages;

- ✓ Psychological support of the first person;

- ✓ Research and interviews;

- ✓ Assessment of external factors;

- ✓ Staff training;

- ✓ Development of media materials and communication of unwanted messages;

- ✓ Analysis of the result in a time interval.

To get the least damage from a crisis, you need to start preparing for it before the crisis actually starts. During a crisis, the first thing that often develops is spontaneity. Motivated managers, in case of danger, make anti-crisis strategies in advance, create scenarios and strengthen personnel. In particular, several stages are implemented to restore normal functioning:

- Anticipation of crisis and continuous preparations before its occurrence;

- To overcome the crisis, determine its maturity period and slow it down;

- Stabilize the situation by using additional resources;

- Calculation of risks, creation of necessary conditions for elimination and gradual exit from the crisis.

Innovative companies with a team of qualified professionals in Georgia and EU countries use this type of management style in their activities.

The innovative company's anti-crisis strategy involves its accurate resource provision, which is a very difficult task in the conditions of the instability of the external environment. Nevertheless, such situations are also subject to resolution if appropriate efforts are made. Defining the anti-crisis strategy has an important role in regulating the company's situation. If the company takes into account the following models before an adverse situation occurs, it will be possible to predict the future, which will help in assessing the damage and developing solutions. In particular:

- SWOT-analysis, identification of threats and business relations, which determines the strengths and weaknesses of the resource potential;

- To consider the crisis at the current level;

- The company should be considered in the aspect of synergistic effect.

Anti-crisis management should provide an effective response by means of control to company managers before, during and after a crisis, so that the company can maintain the stock of resources that it will need in the future to restore pre-crisis times.

The anti-crisis strategy is the implementation of a peculiar risk management with a complex of measures to bring risky situations into a strict corridor. Risk management is a system of managing risk and economic relations (primarily financial) and includes management strategy and tactics.

It should be noted that the following risk management functions are distinguished in anti-crisis management:

- The function of the management object to which the risk avoidance organization belongs;
- Risky capital investments;
- Works related to risk volume reduction;
- Risk insurance process: Economic relations and connections between subjects of economic processes;
- Functions of management entities, which include forecasting, organization, coordination, regulation, stimulation and control.

Anti-crisis strategic management, as a specific type of management activity, with strict boundary parameters and narrowly targeted orientation, is subject to effectiveness evaluation. According to the objective, the result of anti-crisis strategic management should be the transition of the organization to a higher Economic level of balanced functioning than it was before the crisis. At the same time, if for "external" management (mainly financial management) the final result is settlement with creditors (including taxes) and payment of salaries to staff, for internal management (mainly production management) the main goal is to achieve a financial-economic balance as a means of perfecting the production-economic system result. If in the first case, anti-crisis management usually does not have the continuation of production activities, in the second - its successful result is the basis for further progressive functioning of the organization.

Thus, such a differentiation of the goals of the innovative company's "external" and "internal" anti-crisis management simultaneously divides intermediate goals into management activities. The primary goal of the strategic manager (both existing and externally appointed) and the main intermediate measure of effectiveness (correctness of the course) is to achieve the stability of personnel processes and financial settlement in the team of the crisis innovative company. At the time of extremely limited financial resources, the company's general manager faces the following two closely related tasks: continuing the production process and preventing "explosions" in the team. In addition, the effectiveness indicators of anti-crisis management are the provision of a calm state, the longer the leadership can maintain the business environment in the collective, the higher the correctness (effectiveness) of the anti-crisis management course implemented by it.

It is believed that among the four main types of crisis innovative companies - product development, costs, finance and management - the latter occupies a special place. This is explained by the fact that, if the problem of management and rulers is not solved, it becomes impossible to overcome the other three types of negative events. Regarding the management crisis, it is important that the attempt to overcome it can be unsuccessful when it is not possible to attract the appropriate number of qualified personnel. The shortage of qualified personnel is explained by the fact that, when an in-

novative company enters a crisis zone, qualified personnel at all levels of management leave it first. Such a situation forces the head of a crisis organization to take care of maintaining qualified management personnel. Especially - on own deputies and specialists of subdivisions.

The top management of a crisis innovative company is particularly concerned about ensuring peace of mind by balancing the interests of investors, management and staff. Managers of the organization are obliged to ensure a balance of interests between investors and staff, which has the possibility of partial coincidence only within the framework of the given company. It is known that following the entry of the organization into a crisis situation, the area of convergence of interests "narrows" and may turn into zero, which is a prerequisite for the liquidation of the firm.

To evaluate the congruence of interests of investors, managers and staff, a method is used in which the index of congruence of interests is used as a criterion for the effectiveness of anti-crisis management. In addition, the management of the innovative company is separated from the staff due to its special status in the organization. Namely: on the one hand, it includes a hired staff, which is why its status coincides with the status of staff, but on the other hand, it is responsible for representing the interests of investors in the organization, which distinguishes managers from hired staff and gives signs of an investor. These qualities of the management in the form of the top leaders of the innovative company give it the quality of a separate factor, or an entity that functions with a specific sign (indicator).

Thus, the greater the "field" of coincidence of interests of investors and staff, that is, the wider the management base, the more stable the organization's situation. It would be correct to reject such an attitude. In particular, the broader the management base, the more sustainable the organization. The different proportions of this condition are an indicator of management effectiveness. Since, one of the central problems of the management of the crisis organization becomes the means of expansion of its own base ("governing base"). The conducted studies show that the general management, despite its intermediate position in the organization, still leans towards the interests of the personnel and is more focused on the realization of this part of the Economic complex of the innovative company. In this case, the property status of managers, especially top management, is of decisive importance. Management's distance from ownership institutions (investors) can significantly shrink their resource of strategic capabilities (the degree of trust and authority caused by this shrinking).

Due to the relevance of the topic, we consider it highly appropriate to present the formula "Generalized assessment of an innovative company's ability to neutralize the financial crisis in the short-term prospective period", which is calculated as follows:

$$K = \frac{\text{net cash flow expected total}}{\text{financial obligations average total}}$$

Table N1 Below discusses the scale of the innovative company's crisis financial situation and the possible ways out of it.

Table N1

**The extent of the innovative company's crisis financial situation and
Possible exit directions from it**

Scales of the crisis situation of the enterprise	Rules of Response
A mild financial crisis	Normalization of current financial activities
A deep financial crisis	Full use of internal mechanisms of financial stability
A catastrophic financial crisis	Search for effective forms of rehabilitation (in case of failure, liquidation)

It should be noted that one of the most important factors for modern Georgia, which hinders innovative activities, and, therefore, the country's economic growth, is the financial factor - the lack and availability of funds necessary for financing innovative projects. The main sources of innovation financing are: own and borrowed financial funds, other types of assets; allocations from central, regional and local budgets; Credit issued on the basis of repayment, including state, commercial banks and foreign investors. Companies go through several stages in their operations before a financial crisis occurs. Its prerequisite is:

- ❖ Economic instability, when income is less than expenses;
- ❖ Business instability, when the company cannot cover its debt to creditors;
- ❖ When the company is insolvent, no financial measures will help its activities and it ends with liquidation.

Recently, anti-crisis management of companies has become an important term in Georgia. This is the management of a company in the field of business:

- In the conditions of the general crisis of the economy;
- Management of the company in bankruptcy;
- In conditions of overcoming preventive and negative processes.

It is also important for the company not only to achieve progress, but also to avoid the repetition of the problem. Accordingly, after exiting the crisis, the goal of management should be:

- Creating a reliable reputation of the company's work;
- Increasing the efficiency of business process improvement;
- Analysis and modernization of risk forecast assessment;
- Increasing the company's competitiveness;
- Mutually beneficial cooperation with partner companies.

Anti-crisis management requires high practical and theoretical knowledge from the manager, to determine and make the right decision at the time of compromise. Therefore, every head, especially the general manager, needs to constantly think about the future of the innovative company. Even in acute crisis situations, the strategic thinking of the head should be aimed at creating the basis for high-speed development of the innovative company in the post-crisis stage, for example:

- Formation of the organizational structure of internal company relations;
- Study and processing of technical news;

- Renewal of production base;
- Targeted formation of personnel structure, etc.

The summarizing criterion of anti-crisis management is not to overcome the crisis, but to give the innovative company such organizational-technological quality that ensures its active development after coming out of the crisis situation.

The result of management work in a crisis-innovative company should be the gradual overcoming of organizational stress by branches and directions, which ensures its progress. In this context, we can discuss anti-crisis management as an art of management, in which the ability to maximize erudition, insight, creativity, willpower and display of energy, as well as the ability to charge other people working along side with faith.

The main directions of the formation of the management apparatus, the implementation of which allows the crisis innovative company to maintain the ability to function effectively based on systematic approaches in extreme conditions, lies in creative thinking. Here we are talking about the training of managers in order to effectively overcome the crisis; on the involvement of different categories of the government apparatus in solving anti-crisis tasks; on the formation of groups of psychologically and organizationally trained management personnel; In order to organizationally strengthen the crisis innovative company, the creation of management groups according to the principle of "addition", which ensures the formation of the general manager's team from an intellectual and organizational point of view.

Conclusion: Accordingly, we can conclude that the success of anti-crisis management is related to the qualities of the manager himself, since it depends on him to maintain the company through the introduction of new effective management processes that allow the company to improve. In particular, to overcome the crisis situation, to reorganize the company and modernize the low-profitable production, as well as to change the profile.

Based on the relevance of the mentioned topic, we consider it expedient to form the "management team" in such a way as to exclude possible internal conflicts, which is especially disastrous for the qualified personnel of the innovative company in crisis.

Therefore, it is necessary to perfect the strategic orientation of the organization's anti-crisis management in the wake of the involvement of the country's economy in global market relations and the strengthening of its positions, which is mainly emphasized by the innovative companies with corporate social responsibility

successfully operating in Georgia and the EU countries in the 21st century.

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